

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH "DEMOKRITOS"

European Safety, Reliability &
Data Association

65th ESReDA Seminar

on

*From risk imagination to safety intervention -
Managing risks with knowledge*

Programme

November 14th - 15th, 2024

NCSR Demokritos, Athens, Greece

With the kind support of:

European Safety and Reliability Association and

AGENDA

Day 1 – Thursday, 14 November 2024

Start	End	Agenda item
8:30	9:00	Registration
9:00	9:30	<p>Welcome words from:</p> <p>Mohamed Eid, ESReDA president</p> <p>Konstantinos Eleftheriadis, NCSR Demokritos, INRASTES Director</p> <p>Myrto Konstantinidou, PG Leader- Seminar Chair</p>
9:30	10:15	<p>KEYNOTE 1. It is the assumption that kills you</p> <p><i>Prof. John Stoop</i></p> <p>Chairs: Mohamed Eid and Myrto Konstantinidou</p>
10:15	11:00	<p>SESSION 1. Knowledge and Management</p> <p>Chairs: Eric Marsden and Sever Paul</p>
10:15	10:30	<p>1. Management system for regulatory requirements applicable to environmentally classified industrial facilities</p> <p><i>Emmanuel Plot, Vassishtasāi Ramany, Christophe Coll, Frederic Baudequin</i></p>
10:30	10:45	<p>2. Risk management in a complex multirisk unregulated environment</p> <p><i>Dan Serbanescu</i></p>
10:45	11:00	<p>3. Knowledge creation for resilient cyber-socio-technical systems: framing recent research</p> <p><i>Maria Luisa Villani and Antonio De Nicola</i></p>
11:00	11:30	Coffee break
11:30	12:15	<p>KEYNOTE 2 (online). Technical Language Processing – unlocking information in safety data</p> <p><i>Prof. Melinda Hodkiewicz</i></p> <p>Chairs: Maria Luisa Villani and Antonio Guillen</p>
12:15	13:00	<p>SESSION 2. BAG-INTEL project</p> <p>Chairs: John Stoop and Panayiotis Michael</p>
12:15	12:30	<p>4. Risk-based Customs’ Intrusive Inspection Decision Making: Algorithm & Preliminary Case study</p> <p><i>Lamia Hammadi, Eduardo Souza de Cursi, Mohamed Eid, and Henrik Larsen</i></p>

12:30	12:45	5. Processing heterogeneous data sources for risk management by knowledge graph databases: the case of BAG-INTEL research project <i>Bartolome Ortiz-Viso, Karel Gutierrez-Batista, M. Dolores Ruiz and Maria J. Martin-Bautista</i>
12:45	13:00	6. BAG-INTEL: A Hierarchical Multi-Cloud IoT-Edge-Cloud Architecture for Enhanced Airport Security and Operation <i>George Bardas, Panayiotis Michael, Panayiotis Tsanakas, George Lalas and Henrik Larsen</i>
13:00	14:00	Lunch Break
14:00	15:30	Interactive Session What does a management team, a regulator or a front-line operator need to know and can use in order to manage risks effectively?
15:30	16:00	Coffee break
16:00	17:00	ESReDA Board Meeting (<i>different room</i>)
16:00	17:00	SESSION 3. Risk Assessment Chairs: Effie Marcoulaki and Frank Verschueren
16:00	16:15	7. Quantitative Assessment of Landslide Risk to Residents on the Slope of a Hazardous Area in Malaysia. <i>Kwan Ben Sim, Min Lee Lee, Rasa Remenyte-Prescott, Soon Yee Wong</i>
16:15	16:30	8. Risk Assessment of Liquid Hydrogen in Transfer Operations <i>Olga Aneziris</i>
16:30	16:45	9. Road Tunnel Fire Safety: Introducing a new risk assessment framework as a response to the existing challenges <i>Panagiotis Ntzeremes and Konstantinos Kirytopoulos</i>
16:45	17:00	10. What roles for risk imagination in risk assessment? <i>Sever Paul</i>
17:00	18:00	Meeting of Project Group
		End of Day 1

Day 2 – Friday, 15 November 2024

Start	End	Agenda item
9:15	9:30	Logistics from Seminar chair
9:30	10:15	<p>KEYNOTE 3. Industry talk</p> <p><i>Asterios Lialios, Elefsis Refinery HSE Director, Safety Manager of the year 2024, Helleniq Energy S.A.</i></p> <p>Chairs: Myrto Konstantinidou and Vytis Kopustinskas</p>
10:15	10:45	<p>SESSION 4. Materials</p> <p>Chairs: Ana Lisa Vetere Arellano and Tuuli Tulonen</p>
10:15	10:30	<p>11. Vulnerabilities and disruption risks for the supply chains of the Critical Materials necessary for the clean energy transition</p> <p><i>Michalis Christou, Samuel Carrara, Patricia Alves Dias, Angel Prior Arce, Theodor Kuzov, Nicola Magnani</i></p>
10:30	10:45	<p>12. Safe and sustainable-by-design: The case of nanomaterials</p> <p><i>Effie Marcoulaki</i></p>
10:45	11:15	Coffee break
11:15	12:00	<p>KEYNOTE 4. A science of professional engineering practice: our next step towards a safer engineering industry.</p> <p><i>Bill Hewlett, MA CEng FICE FIET</i></p> <p>Chairs: John Kingston and Peter Kouwenhoven</p>
12:00	13:00	<p>SESSION 5. Critical infrastructures</p> <p>Chairs: Olga Aneziris and Michalis Christou</p>
12:00	12:15	<p>13. Enhancing Cross-Border Risk Assessment for Critical Infrastructure: Challenges, Tools and Recommendations</p> <p><i>Monica Cardarilli, Frédéric Petit, Georgios Valsamos, Ana Lisa Vetere Arellano</i></p>
12:15	12:30	<p>14. Critical Gas-Fired Power Plants in Integrated Natural Gas and Electricity Systems</p> <p><i>Ricardo Fernández-Blanco, David Pozo, and Ricardo Bolado-Lavín</i></p>
12:30	12:45	<p>15. Enhancing resilience in critical infrastructures through innovative pathways – The FIRELOGUE and STRATEGY projects approaches in emergency management</p> <p><i>Georgios Sakkas, Nikolaos Kalapodis, Danai Kazantzidou-Firtinidou</i></p>

12:45	13:00	<p>16. Lessons Learned from Coherent Resilience Tabletop Exercises in the Baltic Region <i>Vytis Kopustinskas, Evaldas Dirginčius, Charles Lynn, Isabel Asensio Bermejo, Lawrence Walzer, Darius Aukščionis, Hrvoje Foretić</i></p>
13:00	14:00	Lunch
14:00	14:30	<p>KEYNOTE 5 (online). Collaborative intelligence and human in the loop for the future of safety critical systems. A human-centred perspective. <i>Maria Chiara Leva</i> Chairs: Zoe Nivolianiti and Mohamed Eid</p>
14:30	15:00	Results of the Interactive Session – audience opinions
15:00	15:30	<p>Closing session - "Seminar takeaways" PG and TPC members</p>
15:30	16:00	Coffee and discussions
16:00		End of seminar

Keynote speakers

Keynote 1. Professor John Stoop	<i>Kindunos Safety Consultancy Ltd</i>
It is the assumption that kills you	
	<p>John Stoop graduated as an aerospace engineer at Delft University of Technology. He is one of the founding fathers of the Safety Science Group at this university and did his PhD on the role of safety in the design process. He has been involved in establishing an independent safety investigation board in the Netherlands. In 2007 he became a professor in forensic engineering and safety investigation at Lund University in Lund, Sweden. His main interest lies in the methodology of safety investigations and the relation with the engineering design community in transport, infrastructure and logistics. To validate the theoretical notions and concepts, he was involved in a series of safety assessment surveys of major transport and infrastructure projects. To this purpose he also is a member of several international safety expert networks such as ESReDA. In this community, he contributed to the development of the notion of Foresight, a proactive and prospective assessment of safety and risks. He is an accredited air safety investigator and member of the International Society of Air Safety Investigators. Together with his PhD's he is finalizing two books; one on safety investigations and one on generative design methodologies. After his retirement, he got involved in the integral safety aspects and inherent risks of major wind turbine developments and their contribution to national policy making options on energy transition.</p>
Abstract	
<p>This contribution reflects on the development of safety science in transport, infrastructure and logistics over a period of 40 years at Dutch universities, professional safety institutes and international networks. The contribution heavily relies on the work of the successive ESReDA Working Groups on safety investigation, the transport safety domain as deployed at Lund University in Sweden, the Delft University of Technology and the University of Applied Sciences in Amsterdam. Resulting in a series of graduate student projects, PhD studies and the author's participation in the international aviation investigation community. This contribution identifies the cornerstones for a generative design perspective, challenging a paradigm shift in safety thinking. Four new tools are introduced, materializing this challenge.</p>	

Keynote 2. Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz	<i>Faculty of Engineering and Mathematical Sciences</i> <i>University of Western Australia</i>
--	---

Technical Language Processing – unlocking information in safety data

Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz came to academic from industry having held roles in operations and maintenance. Her expertise is in maintenance, reliability and safety but over the years she has become increasingly interested in information extraction from unstructured texts to support analysis and predictive work in these domains. Her team’s work in AI is supporting her to ask, and answer, questions with improved confidence in the result (reduce the human error element) and in a fraction of time over manual approaches. The UWA NLP-TLP team produces many open-source tools to assist industry in this area <https://nlp-tlp.org/>

Melinda's past roles have included the Australian National Offshore Petroleum Safety and Environmental Regulator (NOPSEMA) Advisory Board (2017-2022), a \$2M BHP Fellow for Engineering for Remote Operations (2016-2022), METS Ignited Advisory committee, Chair Standards Australia MB19 committee ISO 55000-2 Asset Management (2012-2015), and visiting Fellow at the Alan Turing Institute in the UK. She is currently active representing Australia in ISO TC 184 SC4 Industrial Data committee and in the development and publication of the ISO CD 23726 Industrial Data Ontology. More about her background is <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/persons/melinda-hodkiewicz>

Abstract

In the safety domain we look back to inform the way forward. Our approach to identifying and prioritising risks, the controls we select, and the measures we use to assess the effectiveness of these controls is informed by what has happened in the past. In practice this has meant a reliance on the memories of our people and their life experiences. Quantitative estimates have come from limited and out-of-date generic data sets.

This situation is changing rapidly. Industrial organisations (and regulators) can now data mine information from their own internal historical records. They can extract information from unstructured texts such as incident reports and root cause analyses. These developments will unlock a treasure trove of historical data for safety professionals to examine.

In this talk Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz will discuss this Technical Language Processing opportunity, current developments that enable it, and suggest areas where regulators and organisations would benefit from collaboration in this non-competitive area for the benefit of all.

<p>Keynote 3. Asterios Lialios</p>	<p><i>HSE Director Elefsina Industrial Complex Hellenic Petroleum RSSOPP S.A., Hellenic Energy S.A. Safety Manager of the year 2024</i></p>
---	---

Industry Talk

I have started my career as a Process Engineer in Petrola Hellas Refinery in 2000. I served as an Operations Engineer or as a Head of Dept. in various functions (Production, Oil Movement, Marine). Since 2012 I have been a Health, Safety, Fire Safety and Environment Manager in the Aspopyrgos and/or Elefsina refineries of HELPE. Since then I have been striving for the continuous improvement of the HSE performance of the refineries with a strong focus on standardization, innovation and human behaviour.

Having served in the Oil & Gas industry for more than 23 years and worked with renowned experts from companies like Shell and ExxonMobil, I have the conviction that Safety is not just “a priority” or “a company value”: it is the only sustainable way to operate.

Furthermore, I truly believe that Safety is not just about procedures, certifications and machinery: it is mainly about people, their beliefs, their behaviour and, ultimately, their life. Thus, I believe that the key function of the Health & Safety Manager is communication; with colleagues, with contractors and with society as a whole. For those reasons openness is not a “plus”, it is a “must” in order to cultivate a culture of trust, cooperation and transparency which in turn is the basis for a sustainable Safety Culture.

Keynote 4. Bill Hewlett	<i>MA CEng FICE FIET, Civil & structural engineer</i>
--------------------------------	---

**A science of professional engineering practice:
our next step towards a safer engineering industry.**

Bill built his career in construction, working for leading contractors Costain and Laing O'Rourke. At Costain he held the Group Technical Director position for 14 years. He has worked across most types of civil and structural engineering, in building construction, infrastructure, nuclear and petro-chem. From 2020 he developed his career as a consultant, incorporating the role of Technical Director at the British Board of Agrément 2021-2023. BBA provides fitness for purpose certification of construction products, a process involving detail product assessments, analyses and testing.

From 2009 - 2013 Bill served as a Vice President of the Institution of Civil Engineers and in 2015 was elected to the Board of the Engineering Council, as the ICE's representative. In 2016 he became Chair of SCOSS, the Standing Committee on Structural Safety. In 2010 Bill founded the Temporary Works Forum, which he chaired until 2007; TWf has 200+ corporate members. He has served on a number of Boards including for Thomas Telford Ltd, the Forensic Engineering Journal, Lloyds Register Foundation and the Hazards Forum. He contributes to academic work across the fields of procurement, safety science, engineering management and the philosophy of engineering. He holds an honorary chair at Cardiff University Business School.

Bill's quest is for better engineering. He is recognised for his understanding of engineering safety, and his delivery of organisational competence for engineering success.

Abstract

Society, now and for the foreseeable future, relies on engineering. Engineering performance, and thereby the benefit that it can bring, has been much enhanced by work in the underpinning social, economic and physical sciences. The work of ESReDA, for instance, which has done much to develop safety science, evidences this. But to deliver impact in a project or practical instance of engineering endeavour, we need at least satisfactory performance in all underpinnings, not only perfection in one or a few. A balanced scorecard if you will. So some basic questions emerge: What is the full set of underpinning sciences, are we missing one or two and thereby, for practical purposes, undermining the rest? Are there some other underpinnings we need to recognise? What level of maturity is needed in each underpinning, and what are their relative importance in different circumstances? Added to these questions are complexities created by, for instance, having to balance commercial drivers and societal good, the individual and the team, a highly diverse epistemology, inadvertent influences from client, regulator and others, the call for certainty alongside the imperative to innovate. The speaker has made a career as a practitioner navigating and leading in this complex field. In this keynote he will explain the tools he uses and go on to propose a science of professional engineering practice as a route to assuring safety in, and from, the future practice of engineering.

Keynote 5. Maria Chiara Leva	<i>Senior Lecturer Lead of the Human factors in Safety and Sustainability (HFISS) Technical University of Dublin</i>
Collaborative intelligence and human in the loop for the future of safety critical systems. A human-centred perspective.	
	<p>Maria Chiara Leva is the Lead of the Human factors in Safety and Sustainability (HFISS) research group in Technological University Dublin and a Senior Lecturer in the School of Environmental Health for the same institution. She is a visiting research Fellow in the Centre for Innovative Human systems in Trinity College Dublin. She is the co-founder of Tosca Solutions (www.toscasolutions.com) a Spin out campus company based in NDRC and Trinity College Dublin to offer support for implementing risk management tools customised specifically to the needs of highly regulated environments. Her area of Expertise is Human factors and Safety Management Systems. Chiara holds a PhD in Human factors conferred by the Polytechnic of Milano Department of Industrial Engineering. She is the former chair of The Irish Ergonomics Society and current co-chair of the technical committee for Human factors in the European Safety and Reliability Association.</p>
Abstract	
<p>“Organizations that use machines merely to displace workers through automation will miss the full potential of AI...Tomorrow’s leader will instead be those that embrace collaborative intelligence, transforming their operations, their industries and - no less important - their workforces.” H.J. Wilson and P.R. Daugherty (Human + Machine: Reimagining Work in the Age of AI Harvard Business Review Press, 2018)</p> <p>The need for human in the loop automation is particularly relevant for safety critical industry where industrial accidents related to technological malfunctioning have been diminishing leaving the human error responsible for up to 80% of the accidents. However, even if one of the main aims of introducing automation is often to improve safety by reducing or eliminating human errors; it is often argued that this may simply induce new types of errors.</p> <p>To take full advantage of human machine collaboration, companies must understand how humans can most effectively augment machines, how machines can enhance what humans do best, and how to redesign business processes to support the partnership.</p> <p>The opportunity is that the proliferation of wearable sensors that can track human factors in a non-intrusive manner coupled with the abilities of modern AI systems to integrate heterogeneous data to identify anomalies and safety critical situation can now transform the role of the human in the loop for safety critical systems also.</p> <p>To address this changing and exciting landscape there is a need to consider the followings multidisciplinary aspects:</p>	

- 1) Capability to understand our own limitation as human being and cope/use them as another element of live data for Industry 4.0 (to understand what aspect of human performance can be assessed and monitored considering the new capabilities offered by Neuroergonomics tool such as EEG and Eye tracking and what can be considered a legitimate and ethical aspect to assess. Whether for mutual performance monitoring in a teaming environment or for also self-monitoring and feedback.)
- 2) Capability to harness and analyse live data from for industry 4.0 for control of safety critical process to train new AI algorithms to anticipate safety critical scenarios.
- 3) Capability to create novel hybrid collaborative intelligence frameworks to combine the two main key live data sources to support decision and or anticipate critical scenarios in Human-machine Performance optimizations, whereby the human and the intelligent and or autonomous agents can really work as a team.

In the present talk we will just briefly present some areas of application and the key challenges and opportunities they raise in terms of function allocation, dependability and overall system performance. In this sense a collaborative intelligent creative gesture is an innovation that required a combined effort from an intelligent, robotic or autonomous agent and a human.

About the seminar

Seminar organization

The seminar is jointly organized by ESReDA and Demokritos

Location

National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos", Athens

Chairperson of the seminar

Myrto Konstantinidou (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Technical program committee (TPC)

Myrto Konstantinidou (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Eric Marsden (FonCSI, FRANCE)

Sever Paul (AGIFER, ROMANIA)

Tuuli Tulonen (Tukes, FINLAND)

Frank Verschueren (ret. from Ministry of Labor, BELGIUM)

John Stoop (Kindunos, The NETHERLANDS)

John Kingston (NRI Foundation, The NETHERLANDS)

Maria Luisa Villani (ENEA, ITALY)

Antonio de Nicola (ENEA, ITALY)

Dan Serbanescu (Romanian Academy, ROMANIA)

Peter Kouwenhoven (Expert consultant NOVARTIS, The NETHERLANDS)

Kaisa Simola (EC JRC, The NETHERLANDS)

Olga Aneziris (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Effie Markoulaki (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Zoe Nivolianitou (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Nicolas Dechy (IRSN, FRANCE)

Zsuzsanna Gyenes (Global Industrial Safety Solutions Ltd, UK)

Ana Lisa Vetere Arellano (EC JRC, ITALY)

Vytis Kopustinskas (EC JRC, ITALY)

Zdenko Šimić (PSI, SWITZERLAND)

Bogdan Vamanu (National Institute of Physics & Nuclear Engineering, ROMANIA)

Laila Zemīte (Riga Technical University, LATVIA)

Saulius Gudžius (Kaunas University of Technology, LITHUANIA)

Antonio Guillen (ESReDA)

Micaela Demichela (ESReDA)

Local Organising Committee (LOC)

Myrto Konstantinidou (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Effie Markoulaki (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Cleo Makrigiannaki (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Eleni Bairachtari (NCSR Demokritos, GREECE)

Scope of the seminar

ESReDA's '**Risk, Knowledge, Management**' (RKM) project group (PG) addresses the intricate relationships between risk, knowledge and management, aiming to find new ideas for preventing accidents and improving safety management with better utilisation of knowledge. The RKM PG organises the **65th ESReDA seminar** to foster an exchange of ideas and expert debate. The **National Centre of Scientific Research "Demokritos" in Athens** will provide the forum.

The 65th ESReDA Seminar follows the successful 58th ESReDA Seminar on 'Using Knowledge to Manage Risks and Threats: Practices and Challenges' organised by JRC Institute of Energy (Petten, the Netherlands) and held virtually in June 2021.

Although we are told that we live and work in 'information and knowledge' society, preventing accidents and enhancing resilience, by using the relevant safety knowledge and expertise, is not granted and requires continuous efforts to overcome the hurdles in an 'age of uncertainty'.

The main objective of this forthcoming seminar is to identify the enablers and barriers to the production of knowledge concerning safety risks and resilience and its effectiveness in decision-making and other management and operational activities. The key problematic question we will ask is: 'What does a management team, a regulator or a front-line operator need to know and can use to manage risks effectively?'

The purpose of the seminar is to reflect upon the following topics:

- Organisational characteristics that promote the ability to invest in identifying new threats, in imagining risks in a context of uncertainty.
- Tools and frameworks that facilitate evidence-based decision-making and effective safety interventions.
- Individual and collective capabilities and non-technical skills relevant to the sharing of information (including inconvenient truths) between the sharp end of operations and the blunt end where systems are designed; plans, schedules and standards are established; tradeoffs are made, and resources are allocated.
- Anticipating and managing the information and knowledge that will be needed at different stages of the system life-cycle; evidencing the added value of building synergy between safety and knowledge management;
- Recognising and rewarding the diverse types of expertise needed to identify early warning signs, interpret observations, analyse data, communicate information, and preserve knowledge.
- Specific challenges to ensure that valid information, relevant knowledge, 'proofs' but also 'doubts' are available to regulators, the justice system, the media, and the public.
- Technological innovation for risk knowledge management to improve safety and resilience analysis.
- Democratisation of knowledge through participatory approaches and accessibility of information to non-specialists
- Combination and usage of distributed knowledge in complex risk scenarios for crisis management.
- The importance and the role of technology to analyse and to manage adequately risk knowledge as well as to communicate it effectively.
- The role of culture in risk management and the importance of risk communication.

The 65th ESReDA seminar will be a forum for exploring the above mentioned and other related questions. We aim to discuss theories, concepts, and experiences of enhancing the use of knowledge for better risk analysis, management and governance. Authors are invited to present their research and operational proposals and raise challenges, but also to discuss successes and failures in enhancing risk management through better use of risk knowledge. We want to encourage new ideas, scientific papers, conceptual papers, case studies and cross-sectoral and inter-disciplinary research on the theme of challenges and practices for

using knowledge in risk and resilience analysis, management, and governance. This seminar will bring together researchers, practitioners, specialists and decision-makers to discuss strategies and practical experiences.

Target groups and domains of application

Papers for the seminar are invited from various stakeholders, including practitioners and researchers (industrialists, regulators, safety boards, universities, R&D organisations, engineering contractors and consultants, training specialists) and could address different sectors:

- Energy sector: nuclear and non-nuclear (e.g. fossil, renewables) power plants and networks.
- Process and hazardous industry: oil and gas, chemical and petrochemical facilities, industry 4.0.
- Manufacturing.
- Hydrogen Technology.
- Energy transition.
- Transport (rail, road, air and maritime): supply and distribution network, operations, emerging technologies such as driverless cars and autonomous vessels.
- Aerospace industry.
- Critical infrastructure: electricity, water, telecommunications, information systems.
- Public sector and government.
- Urban planning and management.

This seminar is aimed at addressing issues, risks (industrial, natural, Na-Tech, etc.), threats (malicious, cyber-security, terrorism, etc.) and resilience faced by different industries, critical infrastructures, and urban settlements. Other topics may be included if they fit well within the theme of the seminar and are related to using knowledge to manage risks and threats, such as product safety, food safety, biotechnology, health crises, etc.

About Demokritos

Founded in July 1961 as a Research Centre for Nuclear Research, “**Demokritos**” is today the largest multidisciplinary Research Centre of Greece. It has approximately 180 Researchers in tenured and tenure-track positions, and over 500 Research Personnel working in projects funded mainly by grants from State Funds, the European Union and Private Industries. The Centre consists of five independent Institutes focusing on different scientific fields. The **Institute of Nuclear & Radiological Sciences and Technology, Energy & Safety (INRASTES)** is an interdisciplinary R&D establishment pursuing basic, translational and applied research to address challenges of great scientific and socioeconomic impact in a broad spectrum of scientific and technological fields.

The **System Reliability and Industrial Safety Laboratory (SRISL)** is part of the **Institute of Nuclear & Radiological Sciences & Technology, Energy & Safety Radiation Protection** of NCSR “Demokritos”. The laboratory has been conducting top research on the safety and reliability of industrial systems for almost **35 years** providing industry with relevant tools for the analysis of occupational and industrial accidents, the identification of hazards in industrial installations and the quantitative assessment of risks. SRISL, in collaboration with other European research organisations, focuses its research efforts on problems addressing the support of decisions concerning the management of risk, the land use planning around dangerous sites, the evaluation of the role of the organisational and management systems of a company on the safety of the installations, the assessment and management of emerging risks, and the collection, and analysis of accident data towards increased prediction and prevention of future accidents.

About ESReDA

European Safety, Reliability & Data Association (ESReDA) is a European Association established in 1992 to promote research, application and training in Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS). The Association provides a forum for the exchange of information, data and current research in Safety and Reliability. The contents of ESReDA seminar proceedings do not necessarily reflect the position of ESReDA. They are the sole responsibility of the authors concerned. ESReDA seminar's proceedings are designed for free public distribution. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

ESReDA membership is open to organisations, privates or governmental institutes, industry researchers and consultants, who are active in the field of Safety and Reliability. Membership fees are currently 1000 EURO for organisations and 500 EURO for universities and individual members. Special sponsoring or associate membership is also available.

For more information and available ESReDA proceedings please consult <http://www.esreda.org/>

About ESReDA Project Group on Risks, Knowledge and Management

In 2020, ESReDA launched a project group to address the relationships between risks, knowledge and management. The scope defined is of interest to system designers, operators, managers, maintenance, lawyers, insurers, regulators, and many others working on safety and security including natural hazard management. The scope covers the safety, reliability and security related to multiple hazards and threats (natural, high-risk industry, critical infrastructure, communication and transport systems over different territories etc.) involving all stakeholders (public, operators, regulators and government). Risk management integrates all activities and disciplines related to assessment, identification of early warning signs and emerging risks, foresight, investigation of events and lessons to be learned, management of barriers and lines of defense, reliability, and change of policies and culture. In this context, the keyword knowledge defines the main topic of the project: the endeavour to use knowledge to improve the management and governance of risks (from design to operation and dismantling/decommissioning).